

Matching Trademarks and Voluntary Sustainability Standards: A Dataset for Greek firms

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Abstract

This publication note presents a novel dataset that matches information on trademarks and Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) certifications for Greek firms. Firms engaged in international trade face growing pressure to enhance their competitiveness by investing in innovation, product quality, sustainability, and branding strategies. However, detailed firm-level datasets that capture such intangible dimensions of competitiveness remain scarce. To address this gap, we developed a comprehensive dataset by systematically collecting trademark information from the TMView and WIPO databases, and compiling VSS certification data from 23 specialised online directories as of 2023. Given the fragmented and non-tabular nature of available data, web scraping techniques were employed to extract and structure relevant information at the firm level. The resulting dataset includes variables such as certification type and status, application date, validity periods, and firm names. This resource enables researchers and policymakers to examine the relationship between branding and sustainability strategies, or even, how these relate to export performance and firm behaviour. By combining scattered and previously effort-consuming information, this dataset sets the ground for robust empirical analyses that offer valuable insights into the drivers of competitiveness in global markets.

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1. Introduction

Understanding how firms maintain their competitiveness in the complex global markets is an ongoing discussion in applied economics. While cost efficiency and innovation have long dominated analyses on firm performance, shifts in consumer preferences, regulatory expectations, and market dynamics have highlighted the importance of non-price dimensions—particularly branding and sustainability. Trademarks and Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) seem to be two mechanisms through which firms signal quality, reliability, and commitment to social and environmental values.

Despite their relevance, comprehensive firm-level data combining trademark activity and VSS certification status remain largely unavailable, especially in national contexts where access to administrative records is limited. The lack of an integrated and accessible statistical source capturing both branding and certification efforts at the firm level represents a major empirical gap—one that restricts researchers from studying how firms differentiate themselves through reputation-building and compliance with sustainability standards.

This data note addresses this limitation by documenting the construction of a new dataset that matches information on trademark applications and VSS certifications for Greek firms. The aim is to facilitate future research into the interplay between branding and sustainability strategies, and how these influence firm-level outcomes, particularly for exporters. The dataset also serves as a tool for policymakers seeking to understand the uptake of voluntary standards and intellectual property protection by firms, and how these might support broader goals related to competitiveness, trade integration, and sustainable development.

The dataset is built using a mix of traditional and non-traditional data collection methods, including web scraping of 23 online VSS directories and systematic retrieval of trademark records from the TMView and WIPO Global Brand databases. The final dataset contains harmonised firm-level information on trademark status and characteristics, certification type, validity, and issuer, alongside the name of the holder firm that allows for matching with other firm-level data.

The note proceeds as follows. Section 2 describes the data sources and outlines the procedures used for data collection and validity. Section 3 details the data cleaning steps and the integration process. Section 4 presents the key features of the final dataset, offering descriptive statistics on trademark activity, VSS uptake, and their intersection across firms and sectors. Section 5 outlines potential research and policy applications, and Section 6 concludes with practical information on data access and use.

2. Data Collection

The construction of the dataset required a tailor-made data collection strategy due to the absence of a single statistical source that jointly captures information on firms' trademarks and participation in Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) certification schemes— more broadly, on various intangible assets acquired by firms. This section outlines the data sources, and the methodology adopted to retrieve and organise such information -in each case-, focusing on the two components: trademarks and VSS certifications.

2.1 Trademark Data

Firm-level trademark information was collected from TMView¹, a publicly accessible online platform by the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO). In cooperation with national intellectual property offices across Europe and beyond, TMView is the largest integrated trademark search tool that provides free access to trademark applications and registrations from more than 70 participating intellectual property offices, including those of all EU Member States, the EUIPO, the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), and a growing number of non-EU jurisdictions.

The platform enables users to conduct searches based on various parameters, such as applicant name, trademark name, filing and registration dates, classification (Nice classification codes - identifying the categories of goods and services), and current legal status (e.g., registered, expired, withdrawn). For the purposes of this dataset, searches were conducted by applicant name² using the Advanced Search functionality. This allowed for the identification of all trademark applications and registrations associated with Greek firms as of the year 2023. From each record, we extracted all available variables, including the visual elements of the trademark -logos- (where available) as well as the registration number and jurisdiction.

In addition to data retrieved from TMView, we also incorporated trademark information from the WIPO Global Brand Database.³ WIPO-GBD is a publicly accessible repository managed by the World Intellectual Property Organization. This database aggregates trademark records from multiple national and international IP offices, including those not covered by TMView. The only data that could be retrieved from this source was downloaded simply from WIPO's open data section on a single file and filtered to retain records associated with firms operating in Greece. It complements the TMView data by capturing additional international trademark applications filed under the Madrid System and other national systems, providing a comprehensive view of firms' branding activity. Variables collected from WIPO include trademark name, applicant, international classification codes, registration and filing dates, and current legal status.

TMView's and WIPO-GBD's structured format and legal credibility make them appropriate sources for understanding firms' branding and intellectual property portfolios, especially in contexts where no national registry provides a similarly comprehensive or a user-friendly online resource. The combined use of TMView and WIPO ensures a broader and more internationally relevant coverage of trademark activity, particularly for exporting firms.

2.2 VSS Certification Data

The second component of the dataset collects information on Greek firms certified under Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS). These schemes are increasingly used by firms to demonstrate compliance with environmental, social, and quality-related requirements. Yet no unified repository exists with systematic information on certified firms.⁴ To address this data gap, firm-level information

¹ <https://www.tmdn.org/tmview/#/tmview>

² The registry of firm names used for this purpose was limited to the registered Greek firms.

³ <https://www.wipo.int/en/web/global-brand-database>

⁴ One notable effort toward centralizing certification data is the Certified Business Registry (CBR), a global repository of sustainable businesses managed by the International Trade Centre. As of June 2025, it contains information on certified firms under ten different VSS schemes. Despite the importance of this initiative, the number of covered schemes remains limited, as participation in the platform is voluntary and depends on whether each VSS-setting organization chooses to join.

was retrieved directly from 23 publicly accessible directories and certification databases maintained by individual VSS setting organisations.

Given the heterogeneity of these sources in structure, coverage, and level of detail, data collection was conducted through custom web scraping routines. Each script was adapted to the specific architecture of the VSS platform in question, enabling the automated extraction of firm-level details embedded within HTML tables, drop-down filters, and paginated lists. When directories provided downloadable registries or CSV exports, those were prioritised for accuracy and ease of access. The scraping process was designed to retain the highest level of detail while ensuring comparability across schemes. Extracted variables typically included: firm name, country, product category, certification type and status, issuance and expiration dates, and available contact information.

The resulting dataset includes all Greek firms that hold a valid, expired, suspended, or withdrawn certification under any of the 23 identified VSS schemes as of 2023. In several cases, the data are available at the plant or site level, resulting in multiple entries for the same firm across different locations. Moreover, firms may be certified for more than one standard under a given scheme, and each such case is recorded as a distinct entry to preserve granularity. To ensure usability and transparency, a consistent structure was applied across all entries. Table 1 outlines the key variables included in the VSS firm-level dataset. While every effort was made to harmonise the collected data, the dataset suffers some limitations inherent to the source platforms. Not all VSS schemes report complete contact or location information. Certification status definitions may vary slightly across schemes, and in some cases, data was only available for actively certified firms at the time of collection.

Table 1 – Variable description

Variable	Description
firm_name	It is the name of the firm that holds the certification
standard_name	It is the name or code of the standards that the VSS scheme offers
issue_date	It is the last status update for the firm
expiry_date	It refers to when a firm's certification officially expires or becomes invalid
first_issue_date	It refers to when a firm was first awarded certification under a specific VSS scheme. It helps to track the beginning of the firm's certification Journey
certification_status	It refers to the current standing or validity of a firm's certification under a specific VSS scheme. It indicates whether the firm is actively certified, has expired certification, has been suspended, or has been withdrawn
product_category	It refers to the specific type or classification of products the certification covers. This indicates which types of goods or services a firm is certified for under a particular VSS scheme
country	The country in which the firm operates
address	It shows the complete address of the firm
contact	It refers to the firm's primary contact person, typically an email address
directory_link	It provides a link to the website with information about the firm's certification
vss_name	It refers to the name of the VSS scheme

To provide further context, Table 2 presents the full list of VSS schemes included in the dataset, along with a brief description of their structure, sectoral focus, and communication orientation (e.g. B2B or B2C). This rich heterogeneity of schemes—in terms of sectoral focus, origin, and target audience—broadens the analytical scope of the dataset and enables a detailed investigation of firm-level adoption patterns. Combined with trademark data, this component enables novel empirical exploration of how firms use both sustainability certification and branding tools to enhance their position in competitive markets.

Table 2 – VSS schemes in the database and their description

VSS Scheme	Description
Alliance for Water Stewardship 	It is a private global membership collaboration comprising businesses, NGOs, and the public sector. It was established in 2008 and communicates to both businesses and consumers.
Aluminium Stewardship Initiative 	It is a private global non-profit standards-setting and certification organisation. It was established in 2015 and communicates to businesses and consumers.
Aquaculture Stewardship Council 	It is a private global organisation working internationally with aquaculture producers, seafood processors, feed producers, retail and food service companies, scientists, conservation groups, social NGO's and the public to promote the best environmental and social choice practices in aquaculture. It was established in 2010 and communicates to businesses and consumers.
Better Cotton 	It is a Standard System for sustainable cotton production that covers all three sustainability pillars: environmental, social and economic. It was established in 2009 and communicates to businesses - B2B.
BRCGS food safety, BRCGS Ethical Trade and Responsible Sourcing 	It is a market-leading global brand that helps build confidence in the supply chain by setting global standards. It was established in 1996, and the standards communicated to businesses are B2B.
Bio Suisse International 	It was established as an umbrella organisation in 1981, and it now represents the interests of 7362 Bud label agricultural operations and nurseries and owns the registered trademark Bud.
EPEAT 	It is a private program owned and operated by the Global Electronics Council (GEC), a mission-driven non-profit working to create a world of only sustainable technology products and services. It was established in 2006 and communicates to businesses - B2B.

European Feed and Food Ingredients Safety Certification – EFISC

It is a non-profit organisation that administers the EFISC and GTP Code and their certification, promotes the schemes, and promotes their acceptance in the EU market. It was established in 2010 and communicates to businesses - B2B.

Food Safety System Certification 22000

It is a private standard containing a complete certification scheme for Food Safety Management Systems (FSMS) entirely based on the international, independent standards: ISO 22000. It was established in 2009 and communicates to businesses - B2B

Forest Stewardship Council

It is an international organisation that provides a system for private and voluntary accreditation and independent third-party certification. It was established in 1993 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

Friend of the Sea

It is a private certification standard for products and services that respects and protects the marine environment. It was established in 2008 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

Global Organic Textile Standards – GOTS

It was developed by international standard setters to define globally recognised requirements that ensure the organic status of textiles and provide credible assurance to consumers. It was established in 2002 and communicates to both businesses and consumers.

Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)

It is an independent, not-for-profit organisation that develops sustainability reporting standards used by organisations worldwide to report on their environmental, social, and economic impacts. It was established in 1997 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

GLOBALG.A.P. Risk assessment on social practices, GLOBALG.A.P. Crops, GLOBALG.A.P. Floriculture, GLOBALG.A.P. Aquaculture

It is a brand of smart farm assurance solutions for certifying agriculture, aquaculture, and floriculture – advancing safer and more sustainable farming practices. It was established in 1997 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

ISCC Plus, ISCC EU, SCC PLUS - Voluntary Add-nos

It operates different private certification systems to demonstrate compliance with the legal sustainability requirements specified in the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) II. It was established in 2010 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

LEAF MARQUE

It is a leading global assurance system recognising more sustainably farmed products. It is held by farm businesses that meet the rigorous private standards of sustainable farming practice. It was established in 2003 and communicates to consumers - B2C.

Nature Care Products Standard

It is a private standard that labels products made from natural ingredients that do not harm the environment. It was established in 2011 and communicates to consumers - B2C.

PEFC International - Chain of Custody of Forest Based Products

It is a global alliance of regional and national forest certification systems that promotes sustainable forest management through independent third-party certification. It was established in 1999 and communicates to both businesses and consumers.

Rainforest Alliance – 2020

It is a Certification Program comprising three principal components designed to work closely with each other: Sustainable Agriculture Standard, Assurance System, and Data System and Tools. It was established in 1987 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

REDcert

It is a system for the certification of sustainable biomass. It ensures legal compliance with certification requirements for the sustainable production of biomass. It was established in 2010 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil – RSPO

It is a not-for-profit that unites stakeholders from the 7 sectors of the palm oil industry to develop a set of environmental and social criteria that companies must comply with to produce Certified Sustainable Palm Oil (CSPO). It was established in 2004 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

Social Accountability International – SA8000

It is a global non-governmental organisation that is a policy and implementation leader, working with a diverse group of stakeholders, including brands, suppliers, governments, trade unions, non-profits, and academia. It was established in 1997 and communicates to businesses and consumers.

USDA National Organic Program – NOP

It is a federal regulatory program that develops and enforces consistent national public standards for

organically produced agricultural products sold in the United States. It was established in 1990 and communicates to businesses - B2B.

Source: Standards Map Database

Finally, Table 3 presents the full list of online platforms used to extract VSS certification data for Greek firms. Each website corresponds to a distinct VSS scheme and serves as the primary source for firm-level certification records included in the dataset.

Table 3. List of VSS sites

VSS	Website
Alliance for Water Stewardship	https://a4ws.org/certification/certified-sites/
Aluminium Stewardship Initiative	https://aluminium-stewardship.org/about-asi/members
Aquaculture Stewardship Council	https://asc-aqua.org/find-a-supplier/
Better Cotton	https://bettercotton.org/membership/find-members/
Bio Suisse International Production	https://www.easy-cert.com/htm/zertifikate.htm
BRCGS food safety, BRCGS Ethical Trade and Responsible Sourcing	https://directory.brcgs.com/
EPEAT	https://www.epeat.net/#search
European Feed and Food Ingredients Safety Certification - EFISC	https://www.efisc-gtp.eu/members.php?langue=english&cle_menus=1187970073
Food Safety System Certification 22000	https://www.fssc.com/public-register/
Forest Stewardship Council – FSC – Chain of Custody	https://search.fsc.org/pt/search/?search=Greece&page=1&clear=true
Friend of the Sea	https://friendofthesea.org/certified-products-and-services/?meta-field-company_country=Greece
Global Organic Textile Standards – GOTS	https://global-standard.org/find-suppliers-shops-and-inputs/certified-suppliers/database/search_results?total=37
Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)	https://www.globalreporting.org/reporting-support/services/gri-community/community-members/
GLOBALG.A.P. Risk assessment on social practice	https://database.globalgap.org/globalgap/search/SearchMain.faces
ISCC Plus, ISCC EU, SCC PLUS - Voluntary Add-ons	https://www.iscc-system.org/certification/certificate-database/valid-certificates/

Leafmarque	https://leaf.eco/leafmarque
Nature Care Products Standard	https://natrue.org/our-standard/natrue-certified-world/?database[tab]=brands&prod[pageIndex]=2&prod[search]=&brands[pageNumber]=1&brands[filters][letter]=&brands[filters][country][0]=91
PEFC International	https://pefc.org/find-certified
Rainforest Alliance	https://www.rainforest-alliance.org/business/certification/certificate-search-and-public-summaries/
REDcert	https://redcert.eu/ZertifikateDatenAnzeige.aspx
Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil – RSPO	https://rspo.org/search-members/supply-chain-certificate-holders/
Social Accountability International – SA8000	https://sa-intl.org/sa8000-search/
USDA National Organic Program - NOP	https://organic.ams.usda.gov/Integrity/

3. Data Cleaning and Integration

Following the initial data collection, a structured cleaning and integration process was undertaken to create a coherent and well-structured dataset. Given the heterogeneity in formats, definitions, and data quality across the various sources used, this step was critical to ensure the reliability and consistency of the final output.

3.1 Cleaning Procedures

For both trademark and VSS certification data, initial cleaning focused on standardising key identifiers such as firm names, addresses, and dates. Firm names were frequently recorded in inconsistent ways—due to legal suffixes, use of abbreviations, or typographical differences—and were harmonised through string cleaning techniques and manual curation, especially for the ones reported in Greek. Address fields, when available, were also standardised to assist with disambiguation during the merging process. Duplicate entries were identified and removed where they referred to the same asset held by the same firm.

For the TMView and WIPO trademark data, particular attention was paid to the open and user-driven nature of the search interfaces. Searches conducted by applicant name often returned entries unrelated to the firm of interest, due to name similarities or homonyms. As such, the returned entries were manually reviewed to verify relevance and eliminate unrelated or duplicate records. Firm names were cleaned and standardised to allow reliable merging with the VSS certification database. In addition, the trademark records from TMView and WIPO were harmonised, and duplicate entries were dropped prior to integration to avoid overlapping entries and ensure a clean mapping of each firm's branding activity. This was especially important where firms appeared in both platforms, often due to international filings under the Madrid System (captured by WIPO) and national or EU-level filings (captured by TMView).

A particular challenge arose in the VSS data due to variation in the level of reporting across certification directories. While some schemes provide certification data at the firm level, others report information

at the plant or site level, listing multiple operational locations for the same company. To maintain consistency and comparability across schemes, these site-level entries were aggregated to the firm level during the cleaning process. In doing so, unique certifications held by separate plants were preserved as distinct records but linked back to a single parent firm, enabling an accurate count of certifications per firm without overrepresenting multi-site companies. Certification status variables in the VSS dataset were also normalised across schemes, standardising scheme-specific terms (e.g., “valid,” “certified,” “in force”) into a unified status classification. Finally, observations missing non-critical information (such as expiry dates or product categories) were retained if they could still be uniquely identified.

3.2 Data Integration

The cleaned trademark and VSS datasets were merged at the firm level using the harmonised firm name as the primary key. When name-based merging produced ambiguous matches, secondary fields such as address, sector, and contact information were used to verify identity. All integration procedures were conducted manually or semi-automatically with verification checks to minimise false matches or dropped firms.

The merged dataset captures firms' intangible asset portfolios across two key dimensions: branding (via trademarks) and sustainability (via VSS certifications). Where firms held multiple trademarks or certifications, the data are retained in long format, preserving the full richness of firm-asset relationships and enabling firm-year or asset-level analysis.

3.3 Coverage and Matching Results

The compiled trademark dataset (WIPO and TMview combined) contains 2,911 trademark observations. After deduplication by Applicant_name, we identify 1,362 unique firms. The VSS dataset comprises 2,182 observations, corresponding to 1,540 unique firms after duplicates are removed based on firm_name. The matched dataset contains information for 2,364 individual firms, from which 156 hold both branding and sustainability portfolios.

4. Descriptive Statistics and Dataset Features

This section outlines key characteristics of the data, summarising trademark registrations and Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) certifications among Greek firms. It presents descriptive statistics, explores the overlap between trademarking and VSS adoption, and examines key trends and patterns by category and over time.

4.1 Summary Statistics

The trademarks dataset includes information on 2,911 registered trademarks, corresponding to 1,362 unique firms. On average, each firm holds 2.14 trademarks, with a median of 1 trademark per firm, indicating that while some firms register multiple trademarks, many hold only one. The VSS dataset contains 2,182 observations on sustainability certifications, linked to 1,540 distinct firms, with an average of 1.42 certifications per firm and a median of 1, suggesting that most firms participate in one standard, though a few engage with multiple standards.

In the matched sample—the group of firms that appear in both the trademark and the VSS datasets—firms hold on average 5.15 trademarks and 1.21 VSS certifications. The median number of trademarks per firm in this group is 2, while the median number of certifications is 1. When compared to firms that appear only in the trademark dataset (which hold an average of 2.14 trademarks), the matched firms appear to pursue more intensive branding strategies. This suggests that firms engaging in both sustainability certification and trademark registration may be more market-oriented, possibly due to greater international exposure, sectoral pressures, or a strategic emphasis on signalling quality and compliance through multiple intangible assets.

4.2 Overlap Between Trademark and VSS Firms

The matched dataset allows us to identify the extent to which firms hold trademarks, participate in voluntary sustainability standards, or do both. Graph 1 presents the distribution of firms across these three categories. A substantial percentage of firms (approx. 38%) have registered trademarks but do not appear in the VSS dataset. Almost 56% of firms participate in at least one sustainability certification scheme without holding any registered trademarks. However, this result might be influenced by the trademarks acquiring procedure. Notably, a small but significant share of firms, approximately 7%, appears in both datasets, indicating that these firms are engaging in branding through trademarks and in signalling sustainability through VSS participation. This overlap suggests that firms investing in sustainability certifications may also pursue more sophisticated marketing and intellectual property strategies. Conversely, the presence of firms with only trademarks or only certifications highlight the diverse strategic approaches among businesses, depending on their market orientation, sectoral characteristics, or resource constraints.

Graph 1: Trademark and VSS Overlap

4.3 Trademarks – Descriptive Insights

The analysis of trademark filings by Nice classification reveals distinct patterns in firms' branding strategies. The most frequently cited Nice class (see Graph 2) is Class 29 (meat, fish, dairy products, and other preserved foodstuffs), appearing in 679 trademark records. This is followed by Class 30 (staple foods such as coffee, tea, and cereals) with 528 mentions, and Class 35 (advertising and business services) with 420 mentions. Other prominent classes include Class 42 (scientific and technological services), Class 9 (electrical and scientific apparatus), and Class 41 (education and entertainment), reflecting diversification in the goods and services protected by trademarks. Lower but still notable frequencies are observed for Class 3 (cosmetics and cleaning products), Class 31 (natural agricultural products), Class 16 (paper goods and printed materials), and Class 25 (clothing). These results suggest that firms operating in food-related sectors are the most active in trademark registration, with additional activity in services, consumer goods, and technology-related classifications.

Graph 2: Top 10 Nice Classes

Graph 3 illustrates the annual number of trademark registrations-that we were able to recover for Greek firms-from 2000 to 2024. Overall, the volume of registrations remains relatively stable across the period, with modest fluctuations. There is a gradual upward trend from the early 2000s, reaching a slight peak around 2008, followed by minor year-to-year variation. Despite some volatility, the total number of annual registrations stays within a relatively narrow range, suggesting a consistent but not rapidly expanding pace of trademarking activity. The absence of sharp spikes or declines may indicate structural stability in firms' branding behaviour over time, though the slight increase in the mid-2000s could reflect growing awareness or use of intellectual property tools during that period.

Graph 3: Trademark Registrations Over Time

4.4 VSS Certifications – Descriptive Insights

This section explores descriptive patterns in the adoption of Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) by firms. The analysis provides insights into which standards dominate, how certifications are distributed across firms and industries, and how long firms have maintained their certifications. These descriptive statistics aim to help understanding broad trends in sustainability engagement.

An analysis of the most frequently adopted Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) reveals that a relatively small number of schemes dominate firm-level certification activity (see Graph 4). Among the top five schemes, GLOBAL G.A.P. is the most widely adopted, accounting for 28.64% of certifications. This is followed by Food Safety System Certification (FSSC) 22000 accounting for 19.29%, BRCGS food safety, BRCGS Ethical Trade and Responsible Sourcing for 17.32%, and Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) for 8.16%. Finally, ISCC Plus, ISCC EU, SCC PLUS - Voluntary Add-ons accounts for 6.14%, completing the top five. The remaining 20.44% of certifications fall under a variety of other standards.

Graph 4: Top 5 VSS Schemes

This distribution suggests a concentration around food safety, traceability, and agricultural sustainability standards, reflecting sector-specific compliance pressures, international market demands, and firms' strategic efforts to build credibility, enhance product quality, meet buyer expectations, and access higher-value export markets through recognised sustainability certification frameworks.

The distribution of VSS certifications across NICE sectors (Graph 5) reveals significant concentration in a few industry categories. NICE Class 29, which includes meat, fish, and dairy products, stands out as the most certified sector, accounting for 732 certifications. This is followed by Class 30 (staple foods such as coffee, tea, and bakery goods) with 394 certifications, and Class 31 (raw agricultural products) with 372. These three categories dominate the landscape, collectively representing the bulk of VSS-certified activity. Additional notable sectors include Class 35 (advertising and business services) and Class 16 (paper goods), though with substantially fewer certifications.

The predominance of food and agriculture-related sectors aligns with the global trend of VSS adoption, which is particularly strong in industries with intensive supply chain scrutiny, consumer-facing products, and environmental or ethical concerns. This concentration also reflects the prominence of standards like GLOBAL G.A.P., Aquaculture Stewardship Council, and Food Safety System Certification 22000, which are closely tied to these industries.

Next, we are looking at the certification status. To address missing values in the `certification_status` variable, we used the certification expiry date to infer status for entries where the original value was

missing. Specifically, if a certification had no recorded status but the expiry date was on or after the current date, it was classified as Valid_Active. Conversely, if the expiry date had already passed, the entry was classified as Expired.⁵ This procedure ensured consistency in status classification across entries and allowed us to complete missing fields based on available validity data. The original certification_status variable was dropped after this process, and the cleaned variable (cert_status) was used in subsequent analysis and visualisation (e.g., the pie chart on certification status).

Graph 5: VSS Certifications by Nice Class

Each certification status reflects a distinct phase in the lifecycle of sustainability assurance. Valid_Active indicates that the firm is currently compliant and certified, often signaling operational stability and reputational commitment. Expired designations may result from firms opting not to renew due to cost, shifting priorities, or certification fatigue. Terminated certifications suggest a formal decision by either the certifier or the firm to discontinue participation, which can imply deeper issues or deliberate strategic repositioning. Archived certifications, while no longer active, are preserved for reference—potentially replaced or phased out. Suspended certifications are temporarily inactive, often due to non-compliance or pending corrective actions, while Pending_Under review suggests firms are in the process of certification, awaiting audit completion or approval. Together, these

⁵ We assume that if a different certification status (e.g., "Suspended" or "Withdrawn") had applied, it would have been reflected through an updated expiry date or a separate certification entry under the same VSS scheme; this assumption is supported by the practice of some VSS directories to issue new records when the status of a certification changes.

categories highlight the dynamic nature of sustainability engagement, revealing how compliance is not static but influenced by evolving firm conditions and external verification processes.

Looking at Graph 6, the majority of sustainability certifications in the dataset are currently active, with 47.61% of certifications marked as Valid_Active, indicating that firms maintain ongoing compliance with the requirements of the respective VSS schemes. Meanwhile, 50.62% of certifications are labelled Expired, suggesting that a significant portion of firms have either chosen not to renew their certifications or have experienced lapses in compliance. Smaller shares of certifications fall into other categories: Terminated (1.05%), Archived (0.33%), Suspended (0.20%), and Pending_Under review (0.20%). These statuses capture various stages of the certification lifecycle, including voluntary withdrawal, administrative closure, and transitional audit periods. The predominance of active certifications suggests that firms generally maintain engagement with sustainability standards over time, but the notable expired share may reflect operational challenges, cost considerations, or shifting strategic priorities.

Graph 6: VSS Certification Status

To understand how sustainability engagement varies across firms, we examine the distribution of VSS certifications per firm. The histogram below reveals a highly skewed distribution, where the vast majority of firms hold only one certification. Specifically, 98% of firms have a single certification, followed by 8% holding two, 1.5% holding three, and just 1% holding four. This concentration suggests that most firms engage with VSS in a minimal or targeted manner—likely certifying a single process, product, or plant. However, there are notable outliers: a prominent Greek supermarket chain in the dataset stands out with 137 active certifications, the highest in the sample. This observation

underscores the vast heterogeneity in certification intensity across firms, which could reflect differences in firm size, sector, supply chain complexity, or market orientation. By visualising this distribution, we gain insight into how deeply firms embed sustainability standards into their operations—whether as a symbolic step or a comprehensive strategy.

Graph 7: Number of VSS Certifications per Firm

To assess the longevity of firms' engagement with sustainability standards, we examine the time that has elapsed since their earliest observable VSS certification in the dataset. This metric provides insight into how recently firms have adopted sustainability practices and how embedded these practices are in their current operations. As shown in Graph 8, the distribution is heavily skewed toward more recent certifications. Approximately 60% of observed certifications were first issued within the past 2 to 3 years, and an additional 30% fall within the 1-to-2-year range. Only a small share—about 1% to 3%—are older than 3 years, while very few exceed a 6-year history. Descriptive statistics support this pattern: the mean time since first observable certification is 1.96 years, with a standard deviation of 1.70 years. The minimum observed value is 0 years, while the maximum reaches up to 23 years. This pattern suggests that while a few firms adopted sustainability practices early according to our sample. It is important to note, however, that many VSS schemes do not maintain or disclose full historical certification records. In most cases, only active or recently expired certifications are publicly listed, which means that firms with earlier engagements may not be fully captured. As such, this indicator reflects the *visible* duration of certification rather than a definitive measure of how long firms have participated in sustainability standards. While the data still point to a relatively recent and growing

pattern of VSS adoption among Greek firms, the underlying certification history may be longer than the data suggest.

Graph 8: Years since First Certification

Finally, Graph 9 highlights a significant increase in new Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) certifications among Greek exporting firms in 2023, marking a clear peak compared to previous years. This surge reflects a broader shift within the Greek private sector toward adopting sustainability practices more rapidly and on a larger scale. Firms have increasingly recognised sustainability as a critical factor for competitiveness, particularly in export markets where environmental and social responsibility standards have become more stringent. Several key developments in 2023 help explain this spike. The introduction of the European Union’s Deforestation-Free Products Regulation (EUDR) created new legal requirements compelling firms to ensure supply chains are free from deforestation, making VSS certification an important compliance tool. Additionally, growing consumer demand for sustainably produced goods and high-profile corporate sustainability commitments further encouraged firms to obtain certifications.

These combined factors contributed to 2023 being a pivotal year for sustainability adoption among Greek exporters. However, the number of newly recorded certifications declines after this peak, which could suggest that many firms have completed their initial certification processes or that the market is stabilising after a phase of rapid growth. That said, this finding should be interpreted with caution. Many VSS schemes only report currently valid or recently issued certifications, without offering full historical data. As such, earlier certifications that are no longer active—or those that have been renewed—may not be captured, which could bias the observed timeline of adoption. The drop may

therefore partly reflect a visibility limitation rather than a true decline in certification uptake. Despite this caveat, the observed spike in 2023 still signals growing engagement with sustainability among Greek exporters, suggesting a maturing—but still emerging—landscape of voluntary standards adoption.

Graph 9: New VSS Certifications Over Time

4.5 Data Quality Checks

To ensure the reliability of the empirical analysis, we conducted a series of data quality checks focused on missing information, data completeness by VSS scheme, and the risk of duplicate entries. First, we examined the completeness of firm-level contact and address information within the VSS dataset. Roughly 8.25% of records are missing address information, while a significant 82.72% lack contact details such as emails or phone numbers. This high rate of missing contact data may reflect confidentiality practices or data extraction limitations from public sources.

Table 4. Missing Address and Contact Data

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
miss_address	2,182	0.082	0.275	0	1

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
miss_contact	2,182	0.827	0.378	0	1

Next, we examined which VSS schemes are most commonly associated with incomplete entries of NICE classification. A total of 179 such incomplete entries were identified in the dataset. Table 5 lists the affected schemes and their relative contribution to the missingness.

The Bio Suisse International Production standard accounts for the largest share, with 36 entries, or 20.11% of all incomplete records. This could be attributed to its niche presence and specific data handling protocols. Food Safety System Certification (FSSC) 22000 follows closely, representing 18.44% of incomplete cases. Despite being one of the more prominent schemes in the dataset, this suggests inconsistencies in how data are reported or retrieved across firms certified under this standard. Other frequently affected schemes include ISCC (11.73%), Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) (13.97%), and USDA Organic (7.26%). Smaller shares are also observed for PEFC International (5.59%), Aluminium Stewardship Initiative (5.03%), and Leafmarque (6.15%), which together account for a significant portion of the remaining entries. Interestingly, even globally recognised frameworks like GRI (2.79%) and GOTS (1.12%) appear in the list, suggesting that no scheme is entirely immune to data quality concerns. Some entries (e.g., Aquaculture Stewardship Council, Better Cotton, SA8000, efisc-gtp) appear only once, but are still relevant given the importance of complete information for robust analysis.

This breakdown is useful for understanding which certification systems might present greater challenges in terms of data completeness—either due to fragmented reporting, varying disclosure practices by firms, or limitations in public registry integration. Analysts and policymakers should take these gaps into account when interpreting scheme-specific results or aggregating certification data for policy development and benchmarking.

Table 5. List of VSS Schemes Associated with Incomplete Records of NICE classification

VSS Scheme	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
Bio Suisse International Production	36	20.11	20.11
Food Safety System Certification 22000	33	18.44	38.55
ISCC Plus, ISCC EU, SCC PLUS – Voluntary Schemes	21	11.73	50.28
Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil – RSPO	25	13.97	64.25

VSS Scheme	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
USDA National Organic Program – NOP	13	7.26	71.51
Leafmarque	11	6.15	77.66
PEFC International	10	5.59	83.24
Aluminium Stewardship Initiative	9	5.03	88.27
REDcert	7	3.91	92.18
Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)	5	2.79	94.97
Global Organic Textile Standards – GOTS	2	1.12	96.09
Nature Care Products Standard	2	1.12	97.21
Alliance for Water Stewardship	1	0.56	97.77
Aquaculture Stewardship Council	1	0.56	98.33
Better Cotton	1	0.56	98.89
Social Accountability International – SA8000	1	0.56	99.45
efisc-gtp	1	0.56	100.00
Total	179	100.00	

To further assess the quality and completeness of the certification data, we examined two more dimensions: (i) missing values in the cert_status variable, and (ii) cases with multiple entries per firm and VSS scheme that may reflect potential certification updates. Regarding certification status, 655 records (approximately 30% of the dataset) lacked an explicit cert_status value after initial cleaning. These missing values are overwhelmingly concentrated in a single scheme: GLOBALG.A.P. Risk Assessment on Social Practice, which accounts for over 95% of all missing entries (Table 6). This

suggests that some schemes either do not systematically report certification status or do so using formats not captured during scraping. In parallel, we identified firms with multiple entries under the same VSS scheme. These repeated observations are rare, with only 8 cases flagged. Among them, 7 firms had two certification records under the same scheme, and 1 firm had three. Although infrequent, these may reflect re-certifications, renewals, or changes in certification scope over time and highlight the importance of considering firm-VSS pairs longitudinally when studying certification dynamics.

Table 6. List of VSS Schemes Associated with Incomplete Records of certification status

VSS Scheme	Missing Records	Share of Missing (%)
GLOBALG.A.P. Risk Assessment on Social Practice	625	95.42
Aluminium Stewardship Initiative	14	2.14
Global Reporting Initiative (GRI)	8	1.22
Better Cotton	5	0.76
Nature Care Products Standard	2	0.31
PEFC International	1	0.15
Total	655	100.00

Finally, we addressed potential duplicate risks due to naming inconsistencies or firm-level branching (e.g., separate entries for different plants or subsidiaries). To mitigate this, we introduced a unified identifier—`reference_name`—which harmonises firm names across datasets and helps ensure accurate matching and aggregation of observations. This step is critical for avoiding artificial inflation in counts of certified firms and for ensuring internal consistency across our integrated dataset.

5. Potential Research and Policy Applications

The trademarks and Voluntary Sustainability Standards certifications combined dataset offers significant potential for research across applied economics, firm behaviour, innovation, and sustainability. By bringing together information on both trademarks and VSS, it allows for a more nuanced analysis of how Greek firms take advantage of intangible assets to compete in domestic and international markets. The structure of the data, which captures both the timing and nature of these assets, accommodates a range of empirical questions related to firm behaviour, signalling strategies, and market outcomes.

From a research perspective, the dataset facilitates looking into whether firms that register trademarks or obtain VSS certifications perform better in terms of export activity, market reach, or product diversification. The inclusion of precise filing and certification dates allows for analysis of adoption patterns over time, including whether firms tend to invest in branding before seeking certification, vice versa, or simultaneously. This sequencing may offer insights into strategic behaviour and resource constraints, particularly among small and medium-sized firms.

The data are also well suited to exploring the complementarity between different types of intangible assets. For instance, researchers may wish to examine whether firms that signal environmental or social responsibility through certification are also more likely to engage in branding and product differentiation via trademarks. At the same time, the sectoral and product-level granularity (see Nice classification categories) makes it possible to assess variation in adoption across industries and types of goods or services.

Beyond academic research, the dataset offers important applications for policymakers. It can serve as a monitoring tool to assess the diffusion of sustainability standards among Greek firms and to identify sectors where adoption remains limited. This evidence may support the design of targeted interventions to encourage certification, particularly in sectors of strategic importance or in regions with low adoption rates. Similarly, trademark registration patterns can inform industrial and innovation policy, helping to identify firms that actively invest in reputation and product identity, or even low-scale innovative effort.

In the context of export promotion, firms that hold both trademarks and certifications may be particularly well positioned for international growth. Public agencies could use this information to prioritise such firms for export assistance, training, or market access support. Finally, the data can contribute to broader evaluations of voluntary compliance schemes, offering insight into the extent to which such standards function as credible signals in the market and how they interact with formal regulation or public incentives.

6. Conclusion

This report has presented a novel, integrated dataset linking firms' intellectual property strategies—measured through trademark registrations—with their engagement in Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS). By harmonising information from WIPO, TMView, and multiple VSS setting organisations, we were able to track both branding and sustainability signalling strategies at the firm level in Greece. The resulting dataset covers 2,911 trademark records, 2,182 VSS certifications, and 2,364 unique firms that appear in at least one of the two domains.

Descriptive analysis revealed that while many firms hold only one trademark or certification, those participating in both regimes tend to exhibit greater intensity—registering, on average, 5.15 trademarks and 1.21 VSS certifications. The most frequent VSS schemes include GLOBALG.A.P., FSSC 22000, and BRCGS, with a clear concentration around food safety, traceability, and agro-industrial sustainability. Certification longevity also varies, with most firms having been certified within the past 2–3 years, but some maintaining standards for over a decade. Data quality checks ensured high reliability, despite occasional gaps in contact information or product categorisation.

The dataset offers a rich basis for empirical research on corporate sustainability strategies, signalling theory, market access, and firm innovation. In particular, it enables testing of complementarities between branding and sustainability, the role of sector-specific pressures, and the conditions under which firms choose to pursue both types of signalling.

Practical Information

Data Structure: The final dataset is firm-level, with one row per VSS–trademark combination. Duplicates were resolved using a harmonised reference_name variable.

Geographic Scope: The analysis focuses exclusively on firms based or registered in Greece.

Time Coverage: Trademark data spans from the early 2000s to 2024, while VSS certification records are as recent as 2024.

Licensing: Trademark data is derived from open-access registries (e.g., WIPO, TMView); certification data is sourced from public disclosure platforms of VSS bodies. Researchers should verify licensing terms before redistribution.

Limitations: Some VSS schemes provide limited metadata, especially on contact details and certification status. Manual cleaning was required for firm name standardisation.

Reproducibility: All scripts used for merging, cleaning, and analysis are available in Stata format. Graphs and visual outputs can be reproduced with the accompanying .do files and raw data directories.

In sum, this dataset is a foundation for analysing corporate signalling behaviour in sustainability and branding. It provides a timely, policy-relevant resource for researchers, regulators, and market observers aiming to understand how firms communicate trustworthiness, quality, and compliance in increasingly competitive global markets.